

Southern Partner Fund project: Material requirements of a just electricity system in Lao PDR

Questionnaire for government officials and energy planners

General guidance:

This questionnaire has been designed to be used by staff working on this project based in the National University of Lao. The questions follow a logical structure, from providing an overview of the desired topics, to asking details surrounding energy and material planning. The interviews should be conducted in either English or in Laotian: in English, if the interviewee is either a native speaker or is a proficient English speaker, or in Laotian, if the speaker is not proficient in English or if he/she feels more comfortable using Laotian.

The duration of the interview is: 30 min

The recording will be used exclusively to back-up the responses to questions and to create a transcript that the researchers may work with more easily.

Privacy and consent

1. Do you consent to audio being recorded in this interview?
 Yes
 No
2. Would you like your name to be used in the recording of your responses or would you prefer for your responses to be anonymised?
 Use name
 Anonymise
3. Regardless of what you replied in question 2, do you consent to your name being used in the dissemination of the report from this project as a survey participant?
 Yes
 No
4. Regardless of what you replied in question 2, do you consent to your name being used in the academic paper made in this project as a survey participant?
 Yes
 No
5. Do you understand that your answers will be used to inform academic research on the energy situation and provision of materials in Lao, so your responses will be saved by the Universities involved and analysed?
 Yes
 No

Questionnaire:

A - Personal information

A1	Name of interviewee (in the format: first name LAST NAME, e.g., John DOE)	
A2	Occupation	
A3	Name of employer (company or institution)	
A4	Name of position	
A5	If you have professional experience in other areas, please list them generally (e.g., if you work in electricity planning, but have done work regarding construction of electricity, then please type 'construction, electricity infrastructure')	

B - Electricity and material provision

	Overview of the situation	
B1	Please explain in a few words your professional experience in the areas of energy and materials.	
	Electricity provision	
B2	How is new electricity capacity planned and executed in the country (i.e. which process is followed, which stakeholders are involved, how is financing done)?	
	Material provision	
B3	Based on your experience, how easy would you say it is to obtain "natural" bulk manufacturing materials in Lao? This type of materials can include timber, natural fibres, among others.	<input type="checkbox"/> Extremely easy, many of these materials can be bought locally or imported. <input type="checkbox"/> Relatively easy, some materials cannot be bought locally but they can be imported. <input type="checkbox"/> Not easy locally, there are many barriers for local manufacturing of these materials. <input type="checkbox"/> Not easy trade-wise, there are many barriers for importing these materials. <input type="checkbox"/> It is extremely hard, both from local production and trade perspectives.
B4	Based on your experience, how easy would you say it is to obtain "non-natural" bulk manufacturing materials in Lao? This type of materials can include cement, steel, aluminium, among others.	<input type="checkbox"/> Extremely easy, many of these materials can be bought locally or imported. <input type="checkbox"/> Relatively easy, some materials cannot be bought locally but they can be imported. <input type="checkbox"/> Not easy locally, there are many barriers for local manufacturing of many of these materials. <input type="checkbox"/> Not easy trade-wise, there are many barriers for importing these materials. <input type="checkbox"/> It is extremely hard, both from local production and trade perspectives.
B5	Based on your experience, how easy would you say it is to obtain specialised manufacturing materials in Lao? This type of materials can include bentonite, zinc, wind turbines and their parts, solar panels, among others.	<input type="checkbox"/> Extremely easy, many of these materials can be bought locally or imported. <input type="checkbox"/> Relatively easy, some materials cannot be bought locally but they can be imported. <input type="checkbox"/> Not easy locally, there are many barriers for local manufacturing of many of these materials. <input type="checkbox"/> Not easy trade-wise, there are many barriers for importing these materials. <input type="checkbox"/> It is extremely hard, both from local production and trade perspectives.
B6	Based on your experience, how easy would you say it is to obtain heavy machinery in Lao? This type of machinery can include tractors, excavators, cranes, pumps, mills, among others.	<input type="checkbox"/> Extremely easy, heavy machinery can be bought locally or imported. <input type="checkbox"/> Relatively easy, heavy machinery cannot be bought locally but it can be imported. <input type="checkbox"/> Not easy locally, there are many barriers for local manufacturing. <input type="checkbox"/> Not easy trade-wise, there are many barriers for importing heavy machinery. <input type="checkbox"/> It is extremely hard, both from local production and trade perspectives.
B7	Based on your experience, how easy would you say it is to obtain passenger and	<input type="checkbox"/> Extremely easy, many vehicles can be bought locally or imported.

	commercial vehicles in Lao? This type of vehicles can include motorcycles, cars, vans, or lorries.	<input type="checkbox"/> Relatively easy, some vehicles cannot be bought locally but they can be imported. <input type="checkbox"/> Not easy locally, there are many barriers for local vehicle manufacturing. <input type="checkbox"/> Not easy trade-wise, there are many barriers for importing vehicles. <input type="checkbox"/> It is extremely hard, both from local production and trade perspectives.																					
B8	Based on your previous responses and your experience, can you please describe the main barriers for trade that you have identified (i.e. importing and exporting materials)?																						
B9	Based on your previous responses and your experience, can you please describe the main barriers for local manufacturing that you have identified?																						
B10	Are you familiar with the following terms? If you reply YES to having heard at least one of the terms in question B10, please answer questions B10.1-B10.3.	<table border="1"> <thead> <tr> <th><i>Term</i></th> <th><i>Have you heard of it before?</i></th> <th><i>How familiar are you with the term?</i></th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td>Greenhouse gas emissions</td> <td> <input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No </td> <td> <input type="checkbox"/> Never heard of it. <input type="checkbox"/> I have heard of it, but don't know what it means. <input type="checkbox"/> I know roughly what it means. <input type="checkbox"/> I am familiar with it. <input type="checkbox"/> I am very familiar with it. </td> </tr> <tr> <td>Carbon dioxide emissions</td> <td> <input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No </td> <td> <input type="checkbox"/> Never heard of it. <input type="checkbox"/> I have heard of it, but don't know what it means. <input type="checkbox"/> I know roughly what it means. <input type="checkbox"/> I am familiar with it. <input type="checkbox"/> I am very familiar with it. </td> </tr> <tr> <td>Industrial efficiency</td> <td> <input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No </td> <td> <input type="checkbox"/> Never heard of it. <input type="checkbox"/> I have heard of it, but don't know what it means. <input type="checkbox"/> I know roughly what it means. <input type="checkbox"/> I am familiar with it. <input type="checkbox"/> I am very familiar with it. </td> </tr> <tr> <td>Material efficiency</td> <td> <input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No </td> <td> <input type="checkbox"/> Never heard of it. <input type="checkbox"/> I have heard of it, but don't know what it means. <input type="checkbox"/> I know roughly what it means. <input type="checkbox"/> I am familiar with it. <input type="checkbox"/> I am very familiar with it. </td> </tr> <tr> <td>Resource efficiency</td> <td> <input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No </td> <td> <input type="checkbox"/> Never heard of it. <input type="checkbox"/> I have heard of it, but don't know what it means. <input type="checkbox"/> I know roughly what it means. <input type="checkbox"/> I am familiar with it. <input type="checkbox"/> I am very familiar with it. </td> </tr> <tr> <td>Carbon footprint</td> <td> <input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No </td> <td> <input type="checkbox"/> Never heard of it. <input type="checkbox"/> I have heard of it, but don't know what it means. <input type="checkbox"/> I know roughly what it means. <input type="checkbox"/> I am familiar with it. <input type="checkbox"/> I am very familiar with it. </td> </tr> </tbody> </table>	<i>Term</i>	<i>Have you heard of it before?</i>	<i>How familiar are you with the term?</i>	Greenhouse gas emissions	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input type="checkbox"/> Never heard of it. <input type="checkbox"/> I have heard of it, but don't know what it means. <input type="checkbox"/> I know roughly what it means. <input type="checkbox"/> I am familiar with it. <input type="checkbox"/> I am very familiar with it.	Carbon dioxide emissions	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input type="checkbox"/> Never heard of it. <input type="checkbox"/> I have heard of it, but don't know what it means. <input type="checkbox"/> I know roughly what it means. <input type="checkbox"/> I am familiar with it. <input type="checkbox"/> I am very familiar with it.	Industrial efficiency	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input type="checkbox"/> Never heard of it. <input type="checkbox"/> I have heard of it, but don't know what it means. <input type="checkbox"/> I know roughly what it means. <input type="checkbox"/> I am familiar with it. <input type="checkbox"/> I am very familiar with it.	Material efficiency	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input type="checkbox"/> Never heard of it. <input type="checkbox"/> I have heard of it, but don't know what it means. <input type="checkbox"/> I know roughly what it means. <input type="checkbox"/> I am familiar with it. <input type="checkbox"/> I am very familiar with it.	Resource efficiency	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input type="checkbox"/> Never heard of it. <input type="checkbox"/> I have heard of it, but don't know what it means. <input type="checkbox"/> I know roughly what it means. <input type="checkbox"/> I am familiar with it. <input type="checkbox"/> I am very familiar with it.	Carbon footprint	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input type="checkbox"/> Never heard of it. <input type="checkbox"/> I have heard of it, but don't know what it means. <input type="checkbox"/> I know roughly what it means. <input type="checkbox"/> I am familiar with it. <input type="checkbox"/> I am very familiar with it.
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		<p>Decarbonisation</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No</p>	<p><input type="checkbox"/> Never heard of it. <input type="checkbox"/> I have heard of it, but don't know what it means. <input type="checkbox"/> I know roughly what it means. <input type="checkbox"/> I am familiar with it. <input type="checkbox"/> I am very familiar with it.</p>
		<p>Paris Agreement</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No</p>	<p><input type="checkbox"/> Never heard of it. <input type="checkbox"/> I have heard of it, but don't know what it means. <input type="checkbox"/> I know roughly what it means. <input type="checkbox"/> I am familiar with it. <input type="checkbox"/> I am very familiar with it.</p>
		<p>Nationally Determined Contributions (NDC)</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No</p>	<p><input type="checkbox"/> Never heard of it. <input type="checkbox"/> I have heard of it, but don't know what it means. <input type="checkbox"/> I know roughly what it means. <input type="checkbox"/> I am familiar with it. <input type="checkbox"/> I am very familiar with it.</p>
B10.1	If you replied YES to having heard at least one of the terms in question B10, please answer this. In your opinion, who is pushing for actions to reduce carbon emissions in <u>Lao generally</u> ? (Select as many as applicable)	<p><input type="checkbox"/> The Laotian government <input type="checkbox"/> Local businessmen <input type="checkbox"/> Local investors <input type="checkbox"/> Donor agencies <input type="checkbox"/> Foreign banks <input type="checkbox"/> Foreign investors <input type="checkbox"/> Civil groups <input type="checkbox"/> Other</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> No one</p>	
B10.2	If you replied YES to having heard at least one of the terms in question B10, please answer this. In your opinion, who is pushing for actions to reduce carbon emissions in Lao's <u>electricity sector</u> ? (Select as many as applicable)	<p><input type="checkbox"/> The Laotian government <input type="checkbox"/> Local businessmen <input type="checkbox"/> Local investors <input type="checkbox"/> Donor agencies <input type="checkbox"/> Foreign banks <input type="checkbox"/> Foreign investors <input type="checkbox"/> Civil groups <input type="checkbox"/> Other</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> No one</p>	
B10.3	If you replied YES to having heard at least one of the terms in question B10, please answer this. In your opinion, who is pushing for actions to reduce carbon emissions in <u>Lao's industrial sector</u> ? (Select as many as applicable)	<p><input type="checkbox"/> The Laotian government If you select "The Laotian government", which ministries or entities?</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> Local businessmen <input type="checkbox"/> Local investors <input type="checkbox"/> Donor agencies <input type="checkbox"/> Foreign banks <input type="checkbox"/> Foreign investors <input type="checkbox"/> Civil groups <input type="checkbox"/> Other</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> No one</p>	
B11	In your experience, is any work being done in decarbonising industry in Lao?	<p><input type="checkbox"/> Yes – Go to question B9.1 <input type="checkbox"/> No – Go to question B10</p>	
B11.1	If you answered YES in B11 can you please explain what is being done and for which materials?		
	Additional data sources		
B12	Do you know of any databases around material consumption that are available or could be made available to this project?	<p><input type="checkbox"/> Yes – Go to question B12.1 <input type="checkbox"/> No – Go to next section</p>	

	This is especially important for the material provision section.	
B12.1	If you answered YES in B12, please provide more information and/or access to the database.	

Section C - Additional comments

Is there anything else you would like to add regarding material provision and electricity plants planning and construction?